
Effects of salinity changes on aquatic organisms in a multiple stressor context

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SUMMARY

Under global change, the ion concentration of aquatic ecosystems is changing worldwide. Many freshwater ecosystems are being salinised by anthropogenic salt inputs, whereas many naturally saline ones are being diluted by agricultural drainages. This occurs concomitantly with changes in other stressors, which can result in additive, antagonistic or synergistic effects. We reviewed experimental studies that manipulated salinity and other abiotic stressors, on inland and transitional aquatic habitats, to i) synthesize their main effects on organisms ii) quantify the frequency of joint effect types across studies and iii) determine the overall individual and joint effects and their variation among salinity-stressor pairs and organism groups using meta-analyses. Additive effects were slightly more frequent (54%) than non-additives (46%) across all the studies (n=89 responses). However, antagonistic effects were dominant for the stressor pair salinity and toxicants (18% of N), transitional habitats (14% of N) and vertebrates (15% of N). Meta-analyses showed detrimental additive effects of salinity and other stressors on organism performance. This overall trend was

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consistent across stressor-pairs and organism types, and revealed a greater impact of salinity comparing to other stressor. This finding suggests that strategies to mitigate multiple stressor impacts on aquatic ecosystems should prioritise restoring natural salinity concentrations.

INTRODUCTION

In the face of global change, understanding and predicting the effects of multiple stressors is one of the most pressing challenges in conservation and applied ecology [1,2]. In particular, aquatic organisms are exposed to a growing number of stressors [4,5], such as freshwater salinisation [6–8], water acidification [9,10] or eutrophication [11,12]. Given the heterogeneous nature of these stressors (e.g. physical vs. chemical stressors) and the different mechanisms of actions, the co-occurrence of several of them can result in additive, synergistic or antagonistic effects on organisms (e.g. survival, fecundity, metabolic and growth rates, etc.). Additive effects occur when joint stressor effects (i.e. cumulative effects *sensu* [23]) equal the sum of individual effects. Non-additive effects are reflected by a deviation from the additive response, which can be greater (synergism) or lesser (antagonism) than the sum of individual effects [21] and thus exacerbate or mitigate, respectively, the effects on organism performance [22]. These changes at organism level are the primary and most sensitive responses to stress [Folt et al., 1999], but may ultimately alter community composition [13] and interfere with ecosystem processes and services, which sustain human welfare [14].

In recent years, several meta-analyses have synthesised the results of studies that have tested joint effects of multiple stressors in marine [23–25] and freshwater ecosystems [26] at different organisational levels, from organisms to communities, and have shown contrasting results. While an overall synergistic effect of multiple stressors has been found on marine systems, antagonistic joint effects dominate in freshwaters. However, none has specifically provided a comprehensive review of organism responses of inland aquatic species or populations to the combined effects of salinity changes with other global change stressors.

Human activities, like agriculture or salt mining, together with climatic aridification and rising sea levels are increasing salt concentrations in inland freshwaters and coastal habitats, which produces severe negative economic and biological effects [7,16–18]. Contrarily, freshwater inputs, mainly caused by irrigated agriculture in arid landscapes are diluting naturally saline rivers, estuaries and salt marshes, producing harmful effects [19]. At levels above or below the isosmotic point of organism internal fluids, these changes in salinity can disrupt metabolism and water balance [15]. Therefore, aquatic organisms have evolved different osmoregulation mechanisms to control (intra and extracellularly) the osmotic and dehydration stress [Bradley, 2009](Box 1). However, organism osmoregulation capacities might be insufficient to deal with anthropogenic salinisation and dilution

and, most importantly, it is unknown whether the derived negative effects of these salinity changes can be amplified or mitigated in the presence of additional stressors.

The outcomes of multiple stressor interactions are context-dependent (type of ecosystem, trophic level, response level, response metrics, specific stressor pair, stress intensity and duration, etc.) [22, 23, 26]. At the physiological level, the joint effect of multiple environmental stressors ultimately depends on organism sensitivity [2], the degree of response capacity and overlap in the underlying mechanisms and molecular pathways used to combat their effects. Exposure to one stressor can enhance resistance to another (i.e., antagonistic interaction) if the same protective mechanism can cope with both stressors (cross-tolerance [38,39]) or alternatively, activate distinct mechanisms but dependent signalling regulatory pathways (cross-talk, e.g. Uyhelji et al. 2016). However, the resulting interaction effect depends on the energetic cost of the up-regulated mechanisms. If there are energetic trade-offs between protective mechanisms, exposure to one stressor can compromise the response to other stressor and the general result could be a synergistic effect. Finally, if independent mechanisms and pathways are activated, one stressor would have no effect on the response to the other, and an additive effect should be the most probable outcome. Some cross-tolerance and cross-talk responses involving salinity have been reported (e.g. Pallarés et al., 2017b, Uyhelji et al., 2016, Davies et al, 2012). Thus, the *cross-tolerance/cross-talk* framework originally proposed for cold, desiccation and immune responses in overwintering insects [37] may be useful to yield broad-scale predictions of pair-wise interactions among salinity and other stressors, which would require different management actions [1] (Box 2).

Here we reviewed experimental studies that have explored the combined effects of salinity and other key abiotic stressors associated with global change (e.g. temperature, pH, pollutants, etc.) at organism level on several physiological traits that determine the performance of aquatic organisms across inland (freshwater and saline) and transitional coastal ecosystems (estuaries and salt-marshes). Our aims were to i) synthesize the main effects of salinity and other stressors at organism level and identify gaps in the salinity-multistressor literature, ii) quantify the frequency of additive, synergistic and antagonistic joint effects and iii) determine the overall individual and joint effects and their variation among salinity-stressor pairs and organism groups.

METHODS

Bibliographic search and screening

We focused on experimental studies that have assessed multiple stressor effects on the individual performance of organisms (autotrophs, invertebrates and vertebrates) of inland fresh and saline waters, along with estuarine and salt marsh habitats (transitional habitats). We searched the literature

using Web of Science (last accessed on June 2018) with the following sequence of field tags and Boolean operators in advanced searches: (((((TS= ((salin* OR *osmotic* OR conductivity) AND (temperature OR heat OR thermal OR hypoxia OR nutrient* OR radiation OR humidity OR drought OR dehydration OR desiccation OR *ionic* OR pollut* OR insecticide OR pesticide OR acidity OR "pH" OR metals) AND (freshwater OR aquatic NOT marine) AND (physiolog*))))))))). We refined the search by *stress** and no restriction on publication year was placed. From the resulting papers, we selected only those that had applied a full-factorial design, including a clearly defined control treatment (or a treatment deemed by the authors to be under non-stressful conditions for any of the stressors), treatments with one level or more of each single stressor and combined treatments of all the stressors. We also included studies from the cited literature of the selected papers that met these criteria, but did not appear in the different searches. From this first filter by experimental design, we obtained two datasets.

The dataset 1 (electronic supplementary material SM1) contained only those studies that statistically tested the interaction effect. These studies were used for an initial exploration of the individual and joint stressor effects reported and to identify knowledge gaps in the salinity-multistressor literature. We retrieved information for each experiment in each study to characterise stressor pairs (salinity – stressor A, plus temperature, nutrients, metals, pesticides, CO₂, hypoxia, sulphate or pH – stressor B), organism (autotroph, invertebrate or vertebrate), habitat (inland freshwater, inland saline or transitional) and response type (survival and tolerance limits; fitness measurements, including metabolic rates, growth and reproduction traits; molecular responses; physiological regulation, including osmotic capacity and metal uptake or accumulation measurements; and behaviour). We determined: i) the significance of individual and joint effects by exploring the results of the statistical analyses performed in each study; ii) the direction of such effects in individual performance terms compared to the control conditions (i.e. negative – worse performance or positive – enhanced performance) by looking at the *post hoc* tests and/or plots with errors. In multilevel experiments (i.e. those with more than two levels for each stressor), we focused on the highest level before the total mortality of individuals because the magnitude and direction of the joint effects could vary across the different levels of each stressor. .

The dataset 2 (electronic supplementary material SM2) was obtained by selecting exclusively those studies that report either raw data or mean, standard deviation and sample sizes for control, single and combined-stressor treatments. These data were used to quantify the frequency of joint effect types and for meta-analyses (see below). In this dataset, we simplified stressor B categories into temperature, desiccation, nutrients and toxicants (including metals, pesticides, pH and sulphates).

Joint effect types and meta-analyses

From dataset 2, we calculated the individual, main and joint effect sizes for each experiment and study using Hedge's d according to factorial meta-analysis methods [33]. Individual effects reflect the response to one stressor alone in relation to the control. Instead, main effects represent the individual stressor effect plus its contribution to the interaction effect, calculated in the presence and absence of the other stressor (see meta-analysis details in the electronic supplementary material SM3). To ensure a positive relationship with performance, we inverted the sign of main and individual effect sizes from experiments using response variables negatively related with performance (e.g. mortality response was converted into survival response by changing the effect size sign). . To make a quantitative assessment of interaction type frequencies, interaction effects were classified using effect sizes according to Crain et al. [23], who considered additive interactions those whose 95% confidence interval (CI) overlapped zero. Synergistic interactions were those in which both individual effect sizes were negative, or one negative and the other positive, and the interaction effect size significantly lower than zero. Antagonistic types occurred when the interaction effect size was bigger than zero and at least one individual effect size was negative. Because studies with two positive individual effects have a different interpretation referring to the interaction effect size, we also inverted the sign of the interactions [23]. For example, when both individual effect sizes are positive, the untransformed positive interaction effect size would reflect synergy, despite increasing performance; the inverted sign would reflect antagonism, which is consistent with our general interaction criteria.

We used a random-effects model meta-analysis to determine the weighted mean effect sizes of the main and joint effects of stressors for the studies included in dataset 2 using the *metafor* R package [35]. Different meta-analyses were performed with the data subsets that allowed consistent analyses by considering a relatively balanced distribution of studies and effect sizes across moderator categories or groups (organism type, habitat). The selected categorical moderators were treated as fixed effects to assess the mean interaction effects at each level of all the categories (where $n \geq 10$) (see the electronic supplementary material SM4 for more details). Firstly, we conducted an overall meta-analysis across all the studies that tested salinity increase effects ($n=85$) and other using organism type as the moderator (autotroph, $n=21$; invertebrate, $n=43$; vertebrate, $n=21$). We conducted meta-regressions to analyse how overall effect sizes varied with time ($n=85$) and respond to absolute salinity ($n=83$) and temperature ($n=38$) changes in magnitude (treatment – control). A second meta-analysis was done for autotrophs ($n=21$) using habitat as the moderator (inland freshwater, $n=10$ vs. transitional, $n=11$). Finally, for the inland saline water invertebrates, three subgroup meta-analyses were run for the following stressor pairs: salinity decrease x temperature

increase $n=16$), salinity increase x temperature increase ($n=29$) and salinity increase x toxicant increase ($n=9$). We assessed publication bias in all the meta-analyses performed in this study by using funnel plots and Rosenthal's fail-safe number (Borenstein *et al.*, 2009).

The codes of the functions used to run all these analyses are available in the electronic supplementary material SM5, which were performed with R version 3.3.2 (R Core Team, 2016).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Of 2157 screened articles, only 64 studies met our experimental design criteria. Of these, 45 papers tested interaction effects and were reviewed, including a total of 209 response traits from 54 distinct species or populations (dataset 1, electronic supplementary material SM1). We obtained quantitative data from 24 papers to determine the frequency of interaction types and conduct the meta-analyses, in which the main effect sizes of stressors and their interaction were estimated for 89 traits of 28 species (dataset 2, see the electronic supplementary material SM2).

Research contributions and gaps in the salinity-multistressor literature

Although many experimental studies have tested the effects of salinity and other stressors in combination, only a small proportion of them have employed full-factorial experimental designs and appropriate analytical approaches to identify non-additive joint effects. In dataset 1, the statistical analyses most frequently used to test interaction effects were ANOVA type models, which assume a simple addition model as the null model [2]. Most studies tested more than two levels of each stressor, but only 2 of the 45 studies considered (Heilmayer *et al.*, 2008 and Santos *et al.*, 2013) used 5 or more treatment levels, essential to establish a reliable stressor-effect relationship from a factorial experiment [2].

Multiple stressor studies are clearly biased toward certain stressor-pairs, habitat and organisms. The most frequently studied stressors in combination with salinity were temperature (34 % of 209 study cases) and metals (24%). However, other relevant stressors have received less attention (e.g. nutrients and desiccation stress). The most represented habitats were transitional ones (55%), followed by inland saline (26%) and freshwater ecosystems (18%). The number of observations made on vertebrate and invertebrate organisms was similar (36 and 34%, respectively), while autotrophs were less represented (30%). Molecular responses (e.g. activity or gene expression of ion transporter and antioxidant enzymes), survival and tolerance limits, as well as fitness measurements (e.g. growth, reproduction and metabolic rates), were the most frequently studied traits (see dataset 1 in the electronic supplementary material SM1).

The individual effect of salinity decreased organism performance in most of the observations (43%, e.g. decreased survival and growth, increased osmolyte concentration in body fluids, changed metabolic rates, etc.) and was positive in only 20% of the responses, most frequently increasing survival or tolerance to heat or cold stress. Similarly, the individual effects of the other stressors (named stressor B, see the Methods section) resulted in worse performance in most cases, but enhanced it in 30% of the cases. Approximately 50% of the studies reported significant non-additive effects of combined stressors, among which most decreased organism performance, mainly survival.

Frequency of additive, antagonistic and synergistic effects

The classification of joint effect types based on effect size estimates (see the electronic supplementary material SM2) yielded a higher frequency of additive (55%) than antagonistic (30%) and synergistic effects (15%). These patterns varied across stressor pairs, habitat or organism categories. Additive effects were more frequent in the stressor-pair salinity x temperature, inland saline habitats and invertebrates. However, antagonistic effects dominated for the combination of salinity with toxicants, and in both transitional habitats and vertebrates (Figure 1).

These results can be discussed within the cross-tolerance/cross-talk framework earlier exposed (Box 2). In the case of high temperature and salinity, different physiological mechanisms are activated (i.e. heat shock and osmoregulatory responses, respectively), so they are more likely to interact in an additive manner, as we generally observed. For example, Garreta-Lara et al. [40] found a strong influence of salinity on the metabolomic profile of the invertebrate *Daphnia magna*, but no significant interaction with temperature. Though less frequent, some synergistic and antagonistic responses between salinity and temperature were also found (e.g. Hopkins et al., 2017; see dataset 2 in the electronic supplementary material SM2), which suggests that the mechanistic relationship between heat and osmotic stress is still not well understood.

Unlike high temperature, common homeostatic and excretory mechanisms are primarily used against the stress induced by salinity and metals, although each particular metal elicits other specific responses once it is accumulated in the organism (Furness & Rainbow, 1990). Partially shared mechanisms and common regulatory pathways could explain the higher frequency of antagonism found in the salinity and the toxicant stressor-pairs from our dataset (most corresponded to osmoconformer estuarine, anadromous and catadromous fish), a pattern which has also been observed in marine ecosystems [23]. For example, De Polo et al. [41] identified enzyme carbonic anhydrase (CA2) as the mechanistic link at the molecular level involved in the antagonistic effects of

copper and osmotic stress on ion homeostasis in the estuarine fish *Cyprinodon variegatus*. In estuarine and marine invertebrates, increased salinity generally protects against the negative effects of metals [42, Heugens et al., 2001], which can be partly explained by competitive interactions with major cations for sensitive ion transport sites [43]. These competitive interactions diminish under low salinity conditions because of lower concentrations of free ions, which facilitate metal uptake [44]. In freshwater, poor osmoregulator species, for which these cross-protective effects of salinity likely play a smaller role, may therefore be much more vulnerable to water pollution by metals than saline species.

Antagonistic interactions between salinity and pesticides are also typical. In this case, neuroendocrine responses may be involved as cholinesterase inhibition is the main mode of pesticide action (Thompson and Richardson 2004). For example, hypersaline acclimation reduces mortality in subsequent exposure to chlorpyrifos in the euryhaline anadromous fish *Salmo trutta*, and it has been suggested that this protective effect could be associated with reduced neuronal signalling at hypersaline conditions [46].

A poorly explored stressor pair, which shares protective physiological mechanisms, is desiccation and salinity. Both stressors disrupt water and ionic balance and thus cross-tolerance might be expected (Box 2). Antagonistic responses to these stressors are common in plants (Tuteja 2007) and have been found in some aquatic insects [32,47], in which the pre-activation of osmoregulatory mechanisms during salinity exposure seems to contribute to minimise water loss during the subsequent desiccation exposure.

Interestingly, in most antagonistic interaction cases, the individual effects of stressors were both negative, meaning that despite such negative impact is mitigated in the presence of both stressors, they still produce a reduction on organism performance (e.g. the upper thermal limit of saline water beetles decreases less after acclimation stressful salinities and temperatures than under each stress alone, Arribas et al., 2012). Opposing individual effects leading to antagonistic interactions typically occur with nutrients, whose positive effects can overcompensate for the negative effect of salinity (e.g. Kamer & Fond, 2001) as happens with toxicants [23]. We also found, among the few cases of synergistic interactions, opposing individual effects (dataset 2), mostly between salinity and toxicants. For example, in cyanobacteria, the activity of the antioxidant enzyme peroxidase increased in the presence of Cu or Cu+NaCl, but not under NaCl alone (Karimi et al. 2017).

Stressor relative or overall magnitude may also play a critical role in determining the physiological response to multiple stressors (e.g. Folt et al, 1999). Here, few of the reviewed studies provided

quantitative stressor-effect relationships, which frequently require a high number of observations across the stress gradient (REF). Therefore, not enough information was available to conduct a deep analysis regarding the importance of stressor intensity on the resulting joint effect. Using our dataset 2, our meta-regressions showed no significant relationships between the absolute salinity and temperature changes on the absolute joint, salinity or stressor effect sizes (ESM X). For the stressor pair salinity-temperature, the magnitude of salinity change was, in average, similar between the study cases with additive and antagonistic joint effects, and lower in the few cases of synergism. The magnitude of change in temperature was similar across the different interaction types and non-significant relationship was found between the absolute temperature change and the absolute joint effect size (SM N). Surprisingly, among the salinity and toxicant study cases, the magnitude of salinity changes in those cases where non-additive effects were higher than additive effects.

Joint effects of multiple stressors also depend on the timing at which they act [22,39]. When stressors operate sequentially, additive effects are more likely to occur because homeostasis can be re-established in the time between exposure to the first and second stressor. However, interactive effects are more frequent when the two stressors act simultaneously or very close in time. Then, a synergistic effect is expected, or either an antagonistic reaction if the physiological response to the first stress is still present when the second stress occurs. However, in our review study, this effect was controlled because the vast majority of the experimental designs included simultaneous exposure to both stressors.

Overall individual and joint stressor effects: Meta-analyses

The meta-analysis conducted on all the salinity increase studies and organism groups revealed an overall additive joint effect ($d=0.527\pm 0.379$, $p=0.164$, $n=85$ Figure 2a, ST3). When this dataset was moderated by organisms, joint effects were also additive for autotrophs ($d=0.464\pm 0.793$, $p=0.559$, $n=21$), invertebrates ($d=0.005\pm 0.952$, $p=0.630$, $n=43$), and vertebrates ($d=1.777\pm 1.117$, $p=0.240$, $n=21$). The individual mean effect sizes of salinity increases ($d=-2.223\pm 0.779$, $p=0.004$, $n=83$) and stressors B ($d=-0.907\pm 0.378$, $p=0.017$, $n=83$) were significantly negative. Remarkably, the mean effect size of salinity was more than two times higher than the effect size of stressor B. Besides, overall salinity effect size became more negative over time ($d=-0.326\pm 0.152$, $p=0.032$, $n=83$). When analysed with organism taken as a moderator, we found significant negative effects of salinity ($d=-3.499\pm 1.593$, $p=0.028$, $n=21$) and stressor B ($d=-2.553\pm 0.796$, $p=0.001$, $n=21$) on autotrophs (Figs. 2b and c).

In the autotrophs sub-group meta-analysis, the joint effects of salinity and stressor B were also additive in both freshwater ($d=1.053\pm 1.402$, $p= 0.452$, $n=10$) and transitional habitats ($d=0.104\pm 1.949$, $p= 0.626$, $n=11$). In the meta-analyses performed with the subset of studies referring to invertebrates occurring in inland saline waters, we found additive overall joint effects for increasing salinity-temperature ($d=0.396\pm 0.324$, $p=0.223$, $n=19$), decreasing salinity-temperature ($d=-0.257\pm 0.215$, $p=0.231$, $n=29$) and increasing salinity-toxicants stressor pairs, ($d=-0.068\pm 0.669$, $p=0.919$, $n=9$) (Figs. 3a, b and c). Salinity increase did not have a significant main individual effect (Figs. 3a and b) but the main effect of dilution was negative ($d = -0.652 \pm 0.23$, $p = 0.005$). Temperature had no significant effect (Figs 3a and 3c), while the individual main effect of toxicants was significantly negative ($d = -0.670 \pm 0.323$, $p = 0.038$, Fig. 3b). Our significant results were generally robust against publication bias according to the symmetry observed in funnel plots and Rosenthal fail-safe numbers greater than critical thresholds (ESMX).

Overall, our findings revealed no interactive effects (i.e. additive effects) of salinity (either increasing salinity or by dilution) in combination with other stressors, which contrast with the overall synergistic effects of salinity and other stressors reported for marine systems [23], and the overall antagonistic effect of multiple stressor pairs found in freshwaters [26]. Nonetheless, our results should be cautiously compared with other meta-analysis studies, for several reasons. First, responses at different organisational level are highly heterogeneous [23]. Second, [23] and [26] did not focused specifically on salinity (it was pooled with other chemical stressors in [26]), but explored instead a wide range of stressor pairs. One possible explanation for the dominance of additive effects and the higher frequency of antagonisms than synergisms in our study is that salinity may frequently act as a dominant stressor, so that the other stressors have little additional effect [Folt et al., 1000 and 2(Schäffer & Piggot)]. Indeed, the overall individual effect of salinity, either as salinity increase or dilution stress, was generally higher respect to the other stressors analysed, such as temperature. This has important implications for management of aquatic ecosystems. Mitigation strategies aimed at reducing the magnitude of salinity changes could reduce significantly the impact on organisms and substantially improve the health of populations and communities, as other authors have previously suggested (Crain et al. 2013, Thompson et al. 2018). In any case, the notable variability in the importance of the interactions types among stressor-pairs in different aquatic systems suggests that responses are highly context-dependent and therefore a general framework for predicting interactions and guide management could be difficult to establish [1].

Our comprehensive review datasets included taxa and habitats with different life-history traits, stressor sensitivities and evolutionary histories (i.e. colonisation from marine or terrestrial

environments, transitions from fresh to saline waters, etc.), as well as a variety of strategies to cope with salinity stress. For example, while most marine and transitional water organisms are osmoconformers, the majority of organisms in saline inland waters are osmoregulators, such as aquatic insects of terrestrial origin [48–50], and can survive with wide salinity fluctuations by a hyper-regulation capacity in freshwater and a hypo-regulation capacity in saline waters [51] (Box 1). Thus, part of the heterogeneity found among salinity-other stressor pairs could be a result of the different capacities of each osmoregulatory strategy to deal with the second stressor, but this should be further studied

Concluding remarks and future perspectives

The multiple stressor studies reviewed herein focus primarily on the combined effects of increasing salinity against increasing temperature or against toxicants (metals and pesticides), while other important stressor combinations have received very little attention (e.g. desiccation or nutrients). The number of multiple stressors experimental studies conducted in inland waters is still limited compared with those on transitional and marine systems. Thus, more research efforts are needed in freshwater and saline inland waters, which are particularly vulnerable to multiple global change pressures [1,52].

Additive effects of salinity and other stressors were prevalent, but antagonistic interactions also occur in some organism groups (vertebrates), habitats (transitional waters) or stressor-pairs (salinity x toxicants). On an individual basis, salinity has a stronger negative effect on organismal performance traits than other stressors, which highlights the need to increase management efforts on anthropogenic salt inputs (Box 2).

From this review, some considerations for future research arise. First, we need to improve our understanding on the mechanisms and pathways by which a single stressor modulates the physiological response of another stressor. Second, to analyze multi-stressor effects, more complex models than additive ones must be applied if stressor-effect relationships and the correlation between organism's sensitivity to each stressor are known. Third, to better understand and predict the effects of ongoing aquatic ecosystems salinisation and dilution processes, it is crucial to explore the role of the origin and evolution of the osmoregulation strategies of aquatic organisms in determine the type of interactions that may arise between salinity and other stressors.

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DATA ACCESSIBILITY

The datasets supporting this article have been uploaded as part of the supplementary material.

AUTHORS' CONTRIBUTIONS

JV conceived, designed, coordinated the study and drafted part of the manuscript; SP participated in the study design, carried out the literature review, data selection and analyses, created Figure 1 and the electronic supplementary material SM1 and SM2 and drafted part of the manuscript; CG-C carried out the meta-analyses, created Figures 2 and 3, the electronic supplementary material SM3, SM4 and SM5, and drafted part of the manuscript; MB-C carried out the literature review, data selection and analyses, and created the electronic supplementary material SM1 and SM2, and the reference lists; DS-F, PA, JAC and AM contributed with experimental data. All the authors discussed the results, the manuscript revision and gave final approval for publication.

COMPETING INTERESTS

We have no competing interests.

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FIGURE CAPTIONS

Figure 1. Frequency distribution of the interaction types across stressor pairs (a), habitat (b) and organism groups (c) estimated from effect size calculations, and categorised following Crain *et al.* [23] classification (see the electronic supplementary material SM2).

Figure 2. Mean effect sizes (Hedge's $d \pm 95\%$ confidence intervals), overall and by organism groups of a) joint effect, b) salinity individual main effect and c) stressors B individual main effect. The number of observations (n) of each analysis is indicated in parentheses. Filled black squares indicate significant effects ($p < 0.05$).

Figure 3. Mean effect sizes (Hedge's $d \pm 95\%$ confidence intervals) on joint and individual main effects on inland saline invertebrates for a) salinisation and temperature; b) salinisation and toxicants; and c) salinity dilution and temperature. Filled black squares indicate significant effects ($p < 0.05$).

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

SM1: Literature review of interactive effects and performance effects of salinity-stressor pairs combinations (dataset 1)

SM2: Effects size calculations of the individual, main, and interaction effect sizes for each experiment and study from dataset 2 using the Hedge's d according to the methods of the factorial meta-analysis.

SM3: Meta-analysis details

SM4: Meta-analysis results

SM5: Meta-analysis R-scripts